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Second contribution to distribution of species of the subfamily Scaritinae (Coleoptera, Carabidae) of the Balkan Peninsula

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SUMMARY. This article follow up article Bulirsch and Pavićević (2008) that recapitulated basic literary data about distribution of Scaritinae from former Yugoslavia: Serbia, Montenegro, Croatia, Slovenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia and Albania and mentioned new findings of many Scaritinae species. New literary data about new findings in studied regions including descriptions of new species are quoted and date about newly identified specimens are added.

KEY WORDS. Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, faunistics, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Slovenia, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

Bulirsch and Pavićević (2008) published basic literary data about Scaritinae from studied parts of Balcan peninsula published e.g. by Apfelbeck (1904); Fedorenko (1996); Drovenik and Peks (1999) and Balkenohl in Löbl and Smetana (2003). In the meantime were either published some next articles either with faunistics data such as Guéorguiev (2007), Paill, Gunczy and Hristovski (2018) from Albania and Hristovski and Guéorguiev B. (2015), Hristovski, Ivanov and Guéorguiev (2021), Hristovski, Mihajlova and Guéorguiev (2016) from North Macedonia or were described new species from studied regions in Bulirsch and Guéorguiev (2008), Čurčić *et al.*, (2018) and Bulirsch and Magrini (2021). Mainly first author determined or revised rather voluminous Scaritinae material. In the following text there are quoted these date from Serbia, Montenegro, Slovenia, North Macedonia,

Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia and Albania. All species are cited under recent valid names: mostly according to Löbl and Smetana (2003) and / or Fedorenko (1996).

Used abbreviations

- Collections CPBL: P. Bulirsch, Praha, Czech Republic; CDPV: D. Pavićević, Belgrade, Serbia; MMNH: Macedonia Museum of Natural History, Skopje, North Macedonia; NMPC: in coll. Národní Museum, Praha, Czech Republic.

- Literature: A: Apfelbeck (1904); BM: Bulirsch and Magrini (2021); BP: Bulirsch and Pavićević (2008) – as cumulation of literary data and revised species; CPVR: Čurčić et al. (2018); D: Drovenik and Peks (1999); F: Fedorenko (1996); GU: Guéorguiev (2007); HG: Hristovski and Guéorguiev (2015); HIG: Hristovski, Ivanov and Guéorguiev (2021); HMG: Hristovski, Mihajlova and Guéorguiev B (2016); LS: Balkenohl in Löbl and Smetana (2003); MB: Magrini and Bulirsch (2005); PHG: Paill, Gunczy and Hristovski (2018):

- Distribution areas: AL: Albania; BH: Bosnia and Herzegovina; CR: Croatia; CRG: Montenegro; MC: North Macedonia; SER: Serbia; SL: Slovenia; SM: Serbia and Montenegro; *: species without literary and findings data but possible in quoted areas.

LIST OF SPECIES

Subfamily SCARITINAE Bonelli, 1810

Tribe CLIVININI Rafinesque, 1815

Subtribe Clivinina Rafinesque, 1815

Genus *Clivina* Latreille, 1802

1. *Clivina collaris* (Herbst, 1784)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, MC, SER, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

MC: N Macedonia, 10.v.2022, Skopska Crna Gora Mt., Brodec, ca 900 m, J. Janák lgt. (CPBL)

2. *Clivina fossor fossor* (Linnaeus, 1758)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC

HMG: MC

PGH: AL

HIG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: NW Albania, 12.iv.2016, S of Skhoöder, Mal Kolaj, P. Vonička lgt. (CPBL)

CR: Zadar, Pag, SE, Rtina Miletici, 31.v-7.vi.2019, leg. D. Frenzel (CPBL)

3. *Clivina laevifrons* Chaudoir, 1842

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CRG, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC: St. Bogorodica Monastery, river Pčinja - **new for North**

Macedonia

HMG: MC: Skopje, Gradski park

PGH: AL

HIG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Reg. Malesia e Madhe, Liqeni y Skhodrës, Koplik, 30.vi.2015 /leg. P.H. Schnitter (CPBL)

CRG: S Montenegro, Rijeka Crnojevića, 8.vii.2010, D. Čagánek leg. (CPBL); S Montenegro, Virpazar, 4.vii.2010, D. Čagánek leg. (CPBL); S Montenegro, Šas env., Šasko jezero, 27.v.2013, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); S Montenegro, Vranjina, Moraća river, 31.v.201, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); Gornji Štoj pr. Ulcinj, 28.v.2015, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); Donji Štoj, sifting, 8.v.2014, A. Šíma leg. (CPBL)

4. *Clivina ypsilon** Dejean, 1830

LITERARY DATA.

BP: Comment: Occurrence is possible and probable, especially in NO SER, AL or MC.

Subtribe **Reicheiina** Jeannel, 1957

Genus *Dalmatoreicheia* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005

5. *Dalmatoreicheia janaki* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005

LITERARY DATA.

BP: CR: Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt. - in single female HT

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

5a) *Dalmatoreicheia maderi* Bulirsch and Guéorguiev, 2008

LITERARY DATA.

GU: cited as an undescribed species

BG: AL (Kruja Al-ban, Mader) in single male HT

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

Genus *Chaetomargoreicheia* Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005

6. *Chaetomargoreicheia lakotai* (Magrini and Bulirsch, 2005)

LITERARY DATA.

MB: CRG: Lovćen Mts. - in single male HT, described in a new subgenus *Chaetomargoreicheia* of the genus *Reicheadella*

BG: Erected this subgenus to a separate genus

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

7. *Chaetomargoreicheia zoufali* (Reitter, 1913) (**Fig. 1**)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH: Ravno - single female HT

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

7a) *Chaetomargoreicheia gljevensis* Ćurčić, Pavićević, Vesović and Rađa, 2018

LITERARY DATA.

CPVR: CR: Gljev near Sinj - in single male HT

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

7b) *Chaetomargoreicheia faillei* Bulirsch and Magrini, 2021 (**Fig. 2**)

LITERARY DATA.

BM: BH: Trebinje, Arenstorff Cave - in single female

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

Fig. 1. *Chaetomargoreicheia zoufali* (Reitter, 1913).

Fig. 2. *Chaetomargoreicheia faillei* Bulirsch and Magrini, 2021.

Fig. 3. *Chaetomargoreicheia radei* Bulirsch and Magrini, 2021.
(Figures are adopted from Bulirsch and Magrini, 2021).

7c) *Chaetomargoreicheia radei* Bulirsch and Magrini, 2021 (**Fig. 3**)

LITERARY DATA.

BM: CR: Neorić, Sutina, Velika pećina - in single female

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

Genus *Reicheadella* Reitter, 19138. *Reicheadella bischoffi* Meschnigg, 1933

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

AL: S Albania, Gjirokastrë env., Selckë env., Malësia e Lunxhërisë Mts, 1980 m, 25.v.2009, R. Mlejnek leg. (CPBL)

8a) *Reicheadella smetanai* Bulirsch and Guéorguiev, 2008

LITERARY DATA.

GU: cited HT as undescribed species

BG: AL: Liqeni i Butrintit - in single female HT

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

8b) *Reicheadella corcyrea* (Reitter, 1884)

LITERARY DATA. -

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Albania mer., 11.v.2016, Ksamil vill. env., A. Šíma leg., 1 male, (CPBL).

COMMENT. To date known only from Greek Island Corfu (Kerkyra). **New species for Albania.**Genus *Reicheidius* Jeannel, 19579. *Reicheidius frondicola* (Reitter, 1881)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, CR, CRG

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

CRG: Montenegro, Kameno vill. env., 420 m, N 42.4727076 E 18.5277473, 4.xi.2023, M. Švarc leg. (CPBL)

Genus *Spelaeodytes* Miller, 1863

10. *Spelaeodytes mirabilis* Miler, 1863

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, CR

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

Tribe **DYSCHIRIINI** W. Kolbe, 1880

Genus *Dyschiriodes* Jeannel, 1941

11. *Dyschiriodes (Chiridysus) extensus* (Putzeys, 1846)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: CR (Rab)

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

12. *Dyschiriodes (Chiridysus) strumosus* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CR, CRG

GU: -

HG: MC: Skopje, Zoološka Gradina, 30.iv.1936, 1 ex., (MMNH) **new for North Macedonia.**

HMG: MC (cited the same specimen as above)

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

13. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) aeneus aeneus* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, SER, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC

HMG: MC

PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Skoped pr. Lezha; Skhodër; Vrinë env. Butrint; Gjirokastrë, water reservoir; Shupenze pr. Debar, Zerkjani river; Shoshaj pr. Burrel, Mat river; Pjezgjë pr. Durrës, Erzen river (CPBL)

BH: Herzegovina, Mostarsko Blato near Mostar; Herzegovina, Žitomislić Monastery near Mostar; Bosnia, Brčko, near Sava river (CPBL)

CRG: Šas env., Šasko jezero; Gornji Štoj pr. Ulcinj; Ulcinj, Ćurke env.; Skadarsko jezero, Virpazar; Skadarsko jezero, Bijelo Polje;

SER: Salakovac env.; Sremska Mitrovica, Sava river (CPBL)

COMMENT. Several findings of many specimens in all regions - used only abbreviated citation of localities.

14. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) agnatus* (Motschulsky, 1844)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, MC, SER, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC

HMG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Fushe Muhor, Drini i Zi river; Shoshaj pr. Burrel, Mat river; E of Tepelenë; W of Lushnjë, Divjakë; 3 km NE Elbasan; Skhodër, Drin river; Shupenzë pr. Debar, Zerkjani river; Bujan pr. Bajram Curri, Valbones river; 7 km E Tepelenë, 35 km NW Tepelenë, Vjosës river; 3 km NE Millot; Berat, Ossum river (CPBL)

COMMENT. Several findings of many specimens in Albania - used only abbreviated citations of localities.

15. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) apicalis* Putzeys, 1846

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, SL

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL. N Albania, Velipojë, 5.vii.2019, J. Jelínek lgt. (CPBL)

CR: Zadar, Pag, SE, Rtina Miletici, 31.v-7.vi.2019, leg. D. Frenzel (CPBL)

CRG: Ulcinj, Zoganjско blato, 5-6.vi.2006, L. Blažej leg. (CPBL)

16. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) auriculatus auriculatus* (Wollaston, 1867)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, CR, CRG, SM

GU: - (expected species for AL)

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Divjakë vill., 4.5 km SW, 5-6.v.2013, leg. P. Jáchymek (CPBL); W Albania, W of Lushnië, Divjakë, Plazhi i Divjakes, 14.iv.2016, leg. Orszulik (CPBL); S Albania, 8.v.2016, Butrint, salt marsh, A. Šíma leg. (CPBL)

COMMENT. **First citation of this species from Albania.**

17. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) bacillus arbensis* (Müller, 1911)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CR(Rab)

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

ALB: Divjakë vill., 4.5 km SW, 5-6.v.2013, leg. P. Jáchymek (CPBL)

18. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *bacillus bacillus** (Schaum, 1857)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: - Comment: all cited data from AL probably belong to ssp. *arbensis*

19. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *chalceus* (Erichson, 1837)

LITERARY DATA.

D: only generally SM.

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

COMMENT. Missing recent findings data nevertheless occurrence of this halophile species in N CR or N SER along Hungarian borders is very probably.

20. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *chalybeus gibbifrons* (Apfelbeck, 1899)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, SER, SL

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Libohovë pr. Gjirokastrë, water reservoir; S of Shkodër, Mal Kola; S of Sarandë, Butrint; Divjakë (CPBL)

CRG: Ulcinjska solana, Kodre env.; Donji Štoj; Skadarsko jezero, Virpazar; Ulcinj, Čurke env.; Zoganje, Zoganjsko blato, Šas, Šasko jezero (CPBL)

COMMENT. Several findings of many specimens in regions- used only abbreviated citations of localities.

21. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *cylindricus hauseri* (Fleischer, 1898)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: CR (Rab)

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Divjakë vill., 4.3 km SW, 5.v.2013, leg. P. Jáchymek (CPBL)

22. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *intermedius* (Putzeys, 1846)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, MC, SER

GU:-

HMG: MC

HIG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

23 *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) laeviusculus* (Putzeys, 1846)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, SER, SL

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

BH: Bosnia, Oštrelj (CPBL)

CR: Croatia (very old specimen, no other data) (CPBL)

CRG: Ulcinj, Zoganjsko blato, 5-6.vi.2006, L. Blažej leg. (CPBL)

COMMENT. **First citation of this species from Croatia and Montenegro.**

Distribution in Croatia based only on very old general date - its occurrence should be confirmed by next findings.

24. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) luticola luticola* (Chaudoir, 1850)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CR, CRG, SL

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

CRG: Ulcinj, Zoganjsko blato, 5-6.vi.2006, L. Blažej leg. (CPBL); Ulcinjska solana, , Kodre env., 29.v.2015, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); S Montenegro, Ulcinjska solana, Kodre env., 26-27.v.2013 and 29.v.2015, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL)

25. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) macroderus macroderus* (Chaudoir, 1850)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: Comment: possible in AL

GU: cited old literary date (Apfelbeck: Buenë)

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: W Albania, W of Lushnië, Divjakë, 14.iv.2016, leg. Orszulik (CPBL); Vlorë prov., Vrinë env., Butrint, saline, 5.vi.2013, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL)

COMMENT. Recent findings confirming its occurrence in Albania.

26. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) minutus albanicus* (Müller, 1922)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, SM

HG: MC: Skopje, Vardar, xii.1937, leg. S. Karaman, 1 ex., (MMNH) **new**

for North Macedoia (as *D. minutus*)

HMG: MC (cited the same specimen as above)

GU: AL

PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: S Albania, Përmet, Vjosa river, 9.vi.2012, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); Dibrë prov., Shupenzë pr. Debar, Zerkjani riv., 490 m, 12.vi.2014, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); 10.v.2013, Borsh vill., drying river, Jan Habarta leg. (CPBL); 5.v.2013, 3 km NE Elbasan vill., Jan Habarta leg. (CPBL); Shkopet pr. Lezha, Mat river, 2.vii.2012, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); 1.5 km SW Xarrë vill., 10.v.2013 /at light, P. Jáchymek lgt. (CPBL); 3 km NE Elbasan vill., 5.v.2013, Dan Čagánek leg. (CPBL); Berat reg., Berat, Ossum river, 5.vi.2012, 58 m, leg. P.H. Schnitter (CPBL); Kukës prov., Bujan pr. Bajram Curri, Valbones river, 200 m, 6.vi.2014, L. Blažej leg. (CPBL); 3 km NE Millot vill., 15.v.2013, P. Jáchymek lgt. (CPBL)

27. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *minutus minutus* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: CR (Zadar env.)

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

COMMENT. This subspecies occurs only very north-western part of revised region. Other findings and quotation very probably belong to *D. m. albanicus*.

28. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *morio* (Putzeys, 1866)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CRG, MC

HG: MC

PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Elbasan prov., Shënevlash - Dushk, 13 km NW Gramsh, Devolit river, 29.v.2013, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL)

29. *Dyschiriodes* (*Dyschiriodes*) *nitidus nitidus* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CRG, MC, SER, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

BH: Herzeg., Hutovo blato, v.2008 (CPBL)

CRG: Virpazar, 4.vii.2010, D. Čagánek leg. (CPBL)

SER: Salakovac near Požarevac, 14.vi.2009, V Zieris leg. (CPBL)

30. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) politus politus** (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: Comment: Occurrence is possible in N SER and MC.

31. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) punctatus?* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

LS: AL

GU: -

BP: Comment. *D. punctatus* is known from SW of Mediterranean area; its finding in Balcan is not expected. All old literary data very probably belong to either *D. minutus minutus* or *D. m. albanicus*.

32. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) pusillus pusillus* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: Comment. Occurrence is possible especially in AL or N SER (it is known from N Greece and S Hungary).

HG: MC: Skopje, Vardar, xii.1937, leg. S. Karaman, 1 ex., (MMNH) new for MC

HMG: MC (cited the same specimen as above)

COMMENT. **First citation of this species from North Macedonia.**

33. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) salinus striatopunctatus* (Putzeys, 1846)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CR, CRG, MC, SL

GU: AL

HG: only cited literary data in LS

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Sarande nr. Butrint; Skhodër, Velipojë; Divjakë; Vrine env. Butrint all (CPBL)

CRG: Ulcinj, Ulcinjska solana, Zogaj env., 27.v.2013, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL)

COMMENT. Several findings of many specimens in Albania - used only abbreviated citation of localities.

34. *Dyschiriodes (Dyschiriodes) tristis** (Stephens, 1828)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: Comment. Occurrence is possible in MC, SL or N SER

35. *Dyschiriodes (Eudyschirius) abditus* (Fedorenko, 1993)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, CR, SL

GU: -

HG: MC: Skopje, Zoološka Gradina, 15.vi.1936, S. Karaman, 1 ex.,
(MMNH) - **new for North Macedonia**

HMG: MC (cited the same specimen as above)

PGH: AL: SW Albania, Fier County, S to SW of the village Kutë, floodplain
of Vjosa river, 12 specimens - 2 of them (CPBL) - **new for Albania**

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

SL: W Slovenia, Tolmin, Soča river, 28.vi.2001, T. Sitek lgt. (CPBL)

36. *Dyschiriodes (Eudyschirius) globosus* (Herbst, 1783)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, MC, SER, SL

GU: -

HG: MC

HMG: MC

HIG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

CR: NW Croatia, Ivanščica Mt., Ivanec env., 3.vi.2004, R. Kmeco lgt.
(CPBL)

CRG: Ulcinj, Donji Štoj, sifting, 8.v.2014, A. Šima leg. (CPBL)

37. *Dyschiriodes (Eudyschirius) gracilis gracilis* (Heer, 1837)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, SER, SL

GU: AL

PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Elbasan prov., Shënevlash -Dushk, 13 km, NW Gramsh, Devolit river,
29.v.2013, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL), S Albania, 7 km E of Tepelenë, Peshtzan
env., Vjosës riv., 20.iv.2016, leg. Orszulik (CPBL)

38. *Dyschiriodes (Eudyschirius) importunus importunus* (Schaum, 1857)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CR, CRG

GU: AL

HG: MC: Skopje: r. Vardar, xii.1937, leg.: S. Karaman; Vodno: s. Gorno
Nerezi, iv.1937, leg.: S. Karaman; Skopje, 7.v.1936, S. Karaman all in (MMNH)
- **new for North Macedonia**

HMG: MC (cited the same specimens as above) PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: S Albania, 8.v.2016, Butrint, salt marsh, A. Šíma leg. (CPBL); NW Albania, 11.iv.2016, S of Skhoöder, Velipojë, seashore, P. Vonička lgt. (CPBL)

CRG: S Montenegro, Ulcinjska solana, Kodre env., 29.v.2015, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL)

39. *Dyschiriodes (Eudyschirius) rufipes* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, CR, SL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

SER: Serbia, Raška [leg.] (NMPC)

COMMENT **First citation of this species from Serbia** based only on one specimen with very old general label - its occurrence should be confirmed by next findings.

40. *Dyschiriodes (Paradyschirius) parallelus ruficornis* (Putzeys, 1846)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, CRG, MC, SER

GU: AL

HG: MC

HMG: MC

PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: 3 km NE Millot vill., 15.v.2013 J. Habarta lgt. (CPBL); W Albania, 21.iv.2016, W of Lushnjë, Divjakë, seashore, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); CW Albania, Pjezgë pr. Durrës, Erzen river, 3.vii.2012, at light, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); Elbasan prov., Kodovjat, 29-30.v.2012, P. Vonička leg. (CPBL); S Albania, 7 km E of Tepelenë, Peshtzan env., Vjosës riv., 20.iv.2016, leg. Orszulik (CPBL); Berat reg., Berat, Ossum river, 5.vi.2012, 58 m, leg. P.H. Schnitter (CPBL)

41. *Dyschiriodes (Paradyschirius) substriatus priscus* (Müller, 1922)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CRG, SER, SL

PGH: AL

HG: -

HMG: -

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

MC: Grešnitsa, vii.1932, 1 specimen (CPBL),

COMMENT: First citation of this species from North Macedonia based only on one old specimen - its occurrence should be confirmed by next findings.

Genus *Dyschirius* Bonelli, 1810

42. *Dyschirius angustatus* (Ahrens, 1830)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, SER, SL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

43. *Dyschirius thoracicus?* (Rossi, 1790) (= *D. arenosus* (Stephens, 1827))

LITERARY DATA.

LS: BH, CR, SM

BP: Comment: Occurrence in quoted areas is doubtful. There are not any recent findings data.

44. *Dyschirius digitatus* (Dejean, 1825)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, CR, CRG, SL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

CR: NW Croatia, Ivanščica Mt., Ivanec env., 3.vi.2004, R. Kmeco lgt. (CPBL)

45. *Dyschirius latipennis* Seidlitz, 1867

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, MC

GU: AL

HG: MC

PGH: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: N Albania, Velipojë, 5.vii.2019, J. Jelínek lgt. (CPBL).

46. *Dyschirius numidicus numidicus* (Putzeys, 1846)

LITERARY DATA.

LS: SM

BP: - Comment: Species was found in Italian part of Istria (Grado) (NMPC). Occurrence is possible especially in NW part of Adriatic coastal area (SL, CR: N Dalmatia).

Genus *Reicheiodes* Ganglbauer, 1891

47. *Reicheiodes (Reicheiodes) alpicola* (Ganglbauer, 1891)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: BH, SL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL. -

48. *Reicheiodes (Reicheiodes) rotundipennis rotundipennis* (Chaudoir, 1843)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: CR, SL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

BH: Herzegovina (CPBL)

CR: W Croatia, Lokve env., Park šuma Golubinjak, Golubinja cave, 30.ix-1.x.2017, J. Brestovanský leg. (CPBL); N Croatia, NP Risnjak, Chata Jedovica, 26.iv.2004, A. Šíma leg. (CPBL); NW Croatia, Breze vill. env., sifting, 7.ix.2012, A. Šíma leg. (CPBL)

SL: 12.ix.2009, Mt. Trnovski Gozd, Paradana ledena jama env., V. Zieris leg. (CPBL)

COMMENT. **First citation of this species from Bosnia and Herzegovina** - based only on one old specimen with general locality - its occurrence should be confirmed by next findings.

Tribe **SCARITINI** Bonelli, 1810

Subtribe **Scaritina** Bonelli, 1810

Genus *Distichus* Motschulsky, 1858

49. *Distichus (Distichus) planus* (Bonelli, 1813)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: Comment: Occurrence possible especially in AL.

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL. Albania, Lushnjë reg., Divjakë W, Laguna Karavasta, Salicornia area, 11.vi.2012, 9 m üNN, leg. P.H. Schmitter (CPBL)

COMMENT. **First citation of this genus and species from Albania.**

Genus *Scarites* Fabricius, 1775

50. *Scarites (Parallelomorphus) laevigatus* Fabricius, 1792

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, SL

GU: AL

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Divjaka, Karavastas lagun, 16.vi.1994 (CPBL)

51. *Scarites (Parallelomorphus) terricola terricola* Bonelli, 1813

LITERARY DATA.

BP: AL, BH, CR, CRG, SER, SL

GU: AL

HG: MC

HMG: MC

PGH: AL

HIG: MC

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: W of Lushnië, Divjakë, Plazhi i Divjakes, 14.iv.2016, leg. Orszulik (CPBL)

52. *Scarites (Scallophorites) buparius* (Forster, 1771)

LITERARY DATA.

BP: -

GU: AL: S Albanien Vlora, Strand, Tiranë, botanical garden - **new for Albania**

NEWLY REVISED MATERIAL.

AL: Albania, W of Lushnië, Divjakë, Plazhi i Divjakes, 14.iv.2016, leg. Orszulik (CPBL)

COMMENT. Confirmation of occurrence in Albania.

CONCLUSION

In previous text there have been actualised faunistic data from studied areas and added new findings of Scaritinae from the same region. The catalogue published by Bulirsch and Pavićević (2008) has been updated: 7 next species were mentioned as new for Albania, one for Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia Montenegro and Serbia, and finally, 6 for North Macedonia; moreover 4 recently described species, *Dalmatoreicheia maderi* from Albania, *Chaetomargoreicheia faillei* from Bosnia and Herzegovina, *Ch. gljevensis* and *Ch. radei* from Croatia, all described in a single holotype, have been added.

From five scaritine species quoted as possible in Bulirsch and Pavićević (2008) already 3 were confirmed: *Distichus planus* (recent finding, identified by first author) and *Dyschiriodes macroderus macroderus* (2 recent findings, identified by first author) in Albania as well as *Dyschiriodes pusillus pusillus* (one old specimen

cited by Hristovski and Guéorguiev (2015)) from Montenegro. Among the other newly cited species finding of *Reicheadella corcyrea* in Albania, a blind and to date endemic species of Greek Island Corfu, is very unexpected; next remarkable species are *Dyschiriodes auriculatus auriculatus*, *D. abditus* and *D. macroderus macroderus* from Albania and *D. laeviusculus* from Croatia and Montenegro.

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